

The influence of health promotion on increasing knowledge regarding bullying among students at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari, Indonesia

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Abstract

Indonesia is one of the countries recorded as having quite a lot of bullying cases. Researches in three large cities in Indonesia, namely Yogyakarta, Surabaya and Jakarta, recorded that 67.9% of high school students and 66.1% of junior high school students experienced bullying. The highest category being psychological violence (exclusion) and the second rank being verbal and physical violence. This study aimed to determine the effect of health promotion on knowledge about bullying among teenagers at Vocational High School 1 Kendari, Indonesia. A quasi-experimental with pre and post-test design without control group design was conducted in this study. The sample was 29 students from grade X at Vocational High School 1 Kendari, taken by accidental sampling technique. Data collection was carried out by filling out pre-test and post-test questionnaires and analyzed using the Wilcoxon two sample tests (data not normally distributed) using the epi info 7 application. The results of the study showed that the statistical test results with a p-value of $0.006 > 0.05$ indicated that there was a significant difference between knowledge about bullying among students before and after being given health promotion. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is an influence of health promotion on increasing students' knowledge about bullying.

Keywords: Bullying; Health Promotion; Knowledge; Students

1. Introduction

Adolescence is a new period in a person's life, which is marked by changes within the individual, both physically, cognitively, socially and psychologically. As a result of the changes experienced during this period, adolescence also form behaviors that attract the attention of other people. This is done by teenagers because they want to get attention from the environment. In this phase, the nature of egoism and a strong desire to be the center of attention emerge by other people. The emergence of egoism during adolescence can trigger acts of violence. One form of adolescent violence that often appears is bullying behavior (1).

Bullying is a term that refers to actions carried out by a person or group against another person who is considered weaker so that the person or group who feels superior or who is more senior than them will act in an inappropriate way and deviate from the established norms. This negative action is carried out continuously and repeatedly, with the aim of causing the victim to be injured to the point of being physically and psychologically helpless (2).

The World Health Organization (WHO) stated that research conducted in 40 developing countries showed that 42% of boys and 37% of girls were victims of bullying. The types of bullying behavior that occur are sexual violence, physical altercations and bullying (3). According to data from the United Nations Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) (2019) regarding the prevalence of cyberbullying in developed countries, the proportion of children and adolescents affected by cyberbullying ranges from 5% to 21%, with girls being more likely to experience cyberbullying than boys (4).

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Indonesia is one of the countries recorded as having quite a lot of bullying cases. Researches in three large cities in Indonesia, namely Yogyakarta, Surabaya and Jakarta, recorded that 67.9% of high school students and 66.1% of junior high school students experienced bullying with the highest category being psychological violence, namely exclusion, and the second rank being verbal and physical violence (5).

Based on data from the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) and Federation of Indonesian Teachers' Unions (FSGI) in 2023, it was recorded that there were 2,355 cases of child protection violations in Indonesia, including 487 cases of victims of sexual violence, 236 cases of victims of physical and/or psychological violence, 87 cases of victims of bullying or harassment, 27 cases of victims of inadequate educational facilities, and 24 cases of victims of educational policies. This survey covers bullying cases that occurred throughout 2023. Bullying cases are still a terror for children in the school environment. Meanwhile, the types of bullying those victims often experience are physical bullying (55.5%), verbal bullying (29.3%), and psychological bullying (15.2%). Meanwhile, cases of bullying at the SMA/SMK education level were 18.75% (6).

Based on data from the online information system for the protection of women and children (SIMFONI PPA) in 2023, it shows that there were 380 cases of violence against children in Southeast Sulawesi (7). Kendari City is the provincial capital and is the largest contributor to cases of violence against children in Southeast Sulawesi (8).

The influence factor of bullying includes differences between teenagers, such as group, economic level, race, traditions, age (class/seniority differences), family conditions and character differences. These differences can lead to bullying actions such as physical violence, verbal violence, non-verbal violence and even sexual harassment. The impacts experienced by victims of bullying can occur in all aspects of life, both physical, social and psychological. Physical impacts occur when bullying is physical violence, which can include wounds, bruises, infections that can occur throughout the body. Social impacts appear from the ability to have poor social adjustments, such as being afraid to go to school and/or afraid to socialize with others. Meanwhile, psychological impacts that often occur include mental disorders such as feelings of uselessness, feelings of lack of self-confidence, feelings of insecurity, feelings of pressure which can trigger depression and even feelings of wanting to commit suicide (9).

Overcoming bullying behavior can be done by creating a healthy school environment. A school that has a positive environment will invite students to feel comfortable in it and encourage them to display their best abilities. One effort that can be made is to provide education about bullying or harassment of teenagers at school. By providing this information, students can increase knowledge and not just provide information related to bullying, but also provide solutions to prevent and overcome bullying cases (10).

SMK Negeri 1 Kendari is a vocational high school that focuses on business and management careers, located in Kendari City South East Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. Students at this school are expected to produce quality graduates who have character, noble character, competence and environmental insight in accordance with developments in the business world, world of work and industry (11). However, if students experience difficulties in the adjustment process, whether psychologically, skills, appearance, or social status in the school environment, this can be a factor that increases the risk of students becoming victims of bullying.

Based on this phenomenon, this research aimed to determine the influence of health promotion regarding bullying among students at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari.

2. Material and methods

The type of this study was a quasi-experimental with pre and post-test without control group design. This study was conducted at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari on May 25 2024. The sample were 29 students of grade X that taken by accidental sampling technique. The variables included dependent variable (knowledge) and independent variable (health promotion). Data collection was carried out by filling out a pre-test questionnaire before counseling and a post-test after counseling. Data normality testing was carried out using Shapiro Wilk because the respondents less than 50 with the following results:

Tabel 1 Pre-Test and Post Test Data Normality Test

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	sig
Pre Test	0.916	29	0.024
Post Test	0.851	29	0.001

Source: Primary Data (May, 2024)

The result of normality test obtained a p-value for the pre-test and post-test, namely 0.024 and 0.001 < α (0.05), respectively. So, it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed. Thus, the statistical test used in the bivariate analysis is a non-parametric test, Wilcoxon two sample test. Data was processed and analyzed by epi info 7 application.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristic of Respondents

The respondents in this study were teenagers at SMKN 1 Kendari in grade X, totaling 29 students. The characteristics of the respondents are as follows:

Table 2 Distribution of Characteristics of Respondents According to Age and Sex at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Years old)		
15	6	20.69 %
16	23	79.31 %
Total	29	100.00 %
Sex		
Male	5	17.24 %
Female	24	82.76 %
Total	29	100.00 %

Source: Primary Data (May, 2024)

Table 1 showed the characteristics of respondents based on age that of the 29 respondents, most of the respondents were 16 years old namely 23 respondents (79.31%) and the remaining 15 years old, 6 respondents (20.69%). Meanwhile, the characteristics of respondents according to sex, majority of respondents were women, 24 respondents (82.76%) and the remaining 5 respondents were men (17.24%).

3.2. The Influence of Health Promotion on Bullying Knowledge of Students

Table 3 Analysis of the Influence of Health Promotion on Bullying Knowledge of Students

Skor								p-value
Score*Measurement	Obs	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Median	Max	Mode	
Pre Test	29	13.7586	2.9720	6.000	14.000	16.000	17.000	0.006
Post Test	29	15.1034	1.7185	11.000	15.000	17.000	17.000	

Source: Primary Data (May, 2024)

Based on table 3, it can be seen that the average knowledge score before health promotion for the 29 respondents was 13.76 with a standard deviation of 2.97. The lowest score was 6 and the highest was 16 with a median or middle value

of 14. Meanwhile, the average knowledge score after counseling for 29 respondents was 15.10 with a standard deviation of 1.72. The lowest score is 11 and the highest is 17 with a median or middle value of 15. This showed an increase in students' knowledge about bullying before and after receiving counseling. The results of statistical tests using the Wilcoxon two sample test obtained a p-value of $0.006 < 0.05$. This result indicated that there was differences in levels of knowledge before and after being given counseling among students. Thus, it can be concluded that there was an influence of health promotion on students' knowledge about bullying at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari.

SMK students are a group of teenagers where during adolescence it is a transition period between childhood and adulthood. During this developmental period, adolescents reach physical, mental, social and emotional maturity. Generally, every teenager have different emotional maturity in living life (12). A person's weak emotions will have an impact on the occurrence of problems among teenagers. One of the problems that teenagers often face related to peer rejection is the emergence of bullying behavior, which is a special form of aggression among peers(13).

Knowledge about bullying is very necessary in minimizing bullying incidents in teenagers, especially those that occur at school. Knowledge is the result of someone's curiosity about something and occurs after sensing that thing. Sensing occurs through a person's five senses, namely sight, hearing, smell, touch and feeling. Some people gain knowledge through sight and hearing. Apart from that, factors that influence knowledge are education, mass media/information sources, social culture, economics, environment and experience (14). Meanwhile, bullying is generally defined as aggressive behavior such as acts of violence, whether physical or verbal, which are carried out repeatedly and where there is an imbalance of power so that it is difficult for the victim to defend himself (15). In this research, what is meant by knowledge about bullying is the entire definition of bullying, such as the meaning of bullying, characteristics of bullying, perpetrators of bullying, reasons for bullying, victims of bullying, types of bullying, examples of bullying behavior, and the impact of bullying (16).

Under the coordination of the Ministry of Health, especially the Directorate of Health Promotion and Community Empowerment, health promotion or outreach activities are part of the government program. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the aim of health education is to change individual or community behavior in the health sector (17). Health education can be delivered through various methods, one of which is lectures. For example, the previous study that conducted at SMAN 8 Maros showed that mental health education through lectures increased teenagers' knowledge from 65% before education to 90% after education (18). The same thing was found other research that showed an increase in adolescent knowledge at SMAN 1 Sitiung from 20% before education to 60% after mental health education. This study result indicated that lecture method was effective in increasing teenagers' knowledge and understanding about mental health (19).

Meanwhile, research at SMA Muhammadiyah 3 Surabaya showed an increase the average pre-test score from 63.55 to 74.13 in the post-test. This means that the counseling carried out was effective in increasing students' knowledge about mental health and preventing juvenile delinquency (20). The related research conducted at SMAN 2 Sukoharjo found that students' knowledge increased from the sufficient to good category, and attitudes from the low to high category with a p-value of 0.001. This means that the mental health promotion provided not only increases students' knowledge but also changes their attitudes positively (21). In addition, other study found that there was a significant increase in the psychological well-being of class XII students after mental health counseling, with a value of Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.007. Overall, the lecture method in mental health education is effective and consistent in improving knowledge, attitudes and psychological well-being of adolescents (22).

4. Conclusion

This result found that there was an increase in the average score of students' knowledges regarding bullying before and after the health promotion was carried out. Thus it can be concluded that there was an influence of health promotion on increasing students' knowledge about bullying at SMK Negeri 1 Kendari. Therefore, it is hoped that schools can implement and routine outreach activities for all students as an additional program to the existing bullying prevention program. Apart from that, varying health promotion methods with other more interesting methods such as group discussions, simulations, and anti-bullying campaigns.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants in this study.

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